

Short communication

FIRST RECORD OF *BATHYTHRIX FORMOSA* (DESVIGNES) (ICHNEUMONIDAE: CRYPTINAE) IN SERBIA

SAŠA S. STANKOVIĆ and VLADIMIR ŽIKIĆ

Department of Biology and Ecology, Faculty of Sciences and Mathematics,
University of Niš, Višegradska 33, 18000 Niš, Serbia
E-mail: sasasta@gmail.com

The genus *Bathythrix* Förster, 1869 belongs to Ichneumonidae, one of the largest family among parasitoid insects. It is placed in the subfamily Cryptinae and the tribe Phygadeuontini, which comprises more than 70 genera worldwide (Yu *et al.*, 2012; Fauna Europaea, 2017). The great majority of Cryptinae are idiobiont ectoparasitoids that attack the pupal or prepupal stages of holometabolous insects, but there are also koinobiont endoparasitoid species. Some species parasitize the egg sacs of spiders (Fitton *et al.*, 1987). The genus *Bathythrix* comprises about 60 species worldwide. In the European fauna, 23 species of *Bathythrix* have been recorded. Only three species have been registered for the territory of Serbia, *B. aerea* (Gravenhorst, 1829), *B. lamina* (Thomson, 1884) and *B. maculata* (Hellen, 1957) (Fauna Europaea, 2017). So far, *B. formosa* (Desvignes, 1860) has not been registered in Serbia; therefore, we report this species as new to the investigated territory.

Bathythrix formosa is a relatively common species, often found in central and northern Europe: Belgium, Great Britain, Finland, France, Germany, Hungary, Latvia, Poland and Sweden (Fauna Europaea, 2017). This ichneumon wasp is often reared from the egg cocoons of some spiders (Sawoniewicz, 1980; Horstmann, 1998). *B. formosa* is recorded from the egg sacs of the following spiders: *Agroeca brunnea* (Blackwall, 1833), *A. proxima* (O. P.-Cambridge, 1871) from the family Liocranidae (Hedwig, 1950; Horstmann, 1998; Schwarz & Shaw, 2010), and *Allagelena gracilens* (C. L. Koch, 1841) from the family Agelenidae (Smith & Desvignes, 1860; Parfitt, 1881; Bignell, 1898).

At first, after the revision of European species of the genus *Bathythrix* by Sawoniewicz (1980), *B. formosa* was considered to be a variety or a form of *Bathythrix fragilis* (Gravenhorst, 1829). However, Horstmann (1998) showed that these two taxa are actually separate species according to morphological criteria and because they have different host spectrums; *B. formosa* parasitizes spider sacs, while *B. fragilis* is a parasitoid of some hymenoptera.

A female specimen of *Bathythrix formosa* (Fig. 2) was reared from a single egg sac of the spider *Agroeca* sp. (Aranea: Liocranidae). Collecting data are as follows: 1♀ Suva Planina (Mt.), Bojanine Vode (43°13'13.6"N 22°06'48.9"E) 11.07.2010, Leg. S. Stanković. The exact locality is shown in the Fig. 1.

Figure 1. Sampling site – Serbia: Suva Planina (Mt.), Bojanine Vode, marked with the black dot.

Adults occur from May to September. Their size can vary between 5-8 mm, with males being somewhat smaller. Body coloration is a combination of black, yellow and brown. Antennae are made up of 24-30 segments, lightly brown in color. Thorax and abdomen brown, rather red-yellow, with black patches. Legs are lighter than the rest of the body, which is mostly yellowish. Ovipositor straight, with black sheets about 2 mm long. *Agroeca* egg sac is spun of white silk, shaped like a wine glass hanging upside down (Fig. 3).

Bathythrix formosa represents an important pest of Liocranidae and Agelenidae spiders. In some cases, it can significantly affect the population dynamics of spider hosts (Rollard, 1990; Finch, 2005). However, there is little information about the influence of *B. formosa* on other species.

Figure 2. Female specimen of *Bathythrix formosa* (Desvignes, 1860) (Photo by S. Stanković)

Figure 3. Spider sac of *Agroeca* sp. (Aranea: Liocranidae) (Photo by V. Žikić)

Acknowledgement: This work was supported by the Ministry of Education, Science and Technological Development of the Republic of Serbia (III43001).

References: Bignell, G. C. (1898). *Transactions of the Devonshire Association for the Advancement of Science, Literature and Art*, 30, 458-504. Fauna Europaea Internet Database (2018). Retrieved from <https://fauna-eu.org/>. [Accessed on: January 2018]. Finch, O. D. (2005). *Journal of Natural History*, 39(25), 2339-2354. Fitton, M. G., Shaw, M. R., & Austin, A. D. (1987). *Zoological Journal of the Linnean Society*, 90(1), 65-93. Hedwig K. (1950). *Nachrichten des Naturwissenschaftlichen Museums der Stadt Aschaffenburg*, 29, 17-42. [In German]. Horstmann, K. (1998). *Entomofauna*, 19, 433-460. [In German]. Parfitt, E. (1881). *Report and Transaction of the Devonshire Association of Advance Science*, 13, 241-292. Rollard, C. (1990). *Acta Zoologica Fennica*, 190, 327-331. Sawoniewicz, J. (1980). *Annales Zoologici*, 35(23), 319-366. Schwarz, M., & Shaw, M. R. (2010). *Entomologist's Gazette*, 61, 187-206. Smith, F., & Desvignes, T. (1860). *Transactions of the Entomological Society of London*, 5(2), 209-211. Yu, D. S., van Achterberg, C., & Horstmann K. (2012). World Ichneumonoidea 2011. Taxonomy, biology, Morphology and distribution (Braconidae). Taxapad – Scientific names for information management) Interactive catalogue on DVD/CDROM. Vancouver.

ПРВИ НАЛАЗ *BATHYTHRIX FORMOSA* (DESVIGNES) (ICHNEUMONIDAE: CRYPTINAE) У СРБИЈИ

САША С. СТАНКОВИЋ И ВЛАДИМИР ЖИКИЋ

Извод

Bathythrix formosa (Desvignes, 1860) је нова врста оса потајница за фауну Србије. Забележена је на локалитету Бојанине воде, Сува планина из домаћина *Agroeca* sp (Aranea: Liocranidae).

Received: March 1st, 2018
Accepted: September 5th, 2018